

Developing Training Corpora for Automatic Extraction of Cybersecurity Terminology

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Abstract. The paper presents the work on the compilation of English and Lithuanian parallel and comparable corpora with manually annotated cybersecurity terminology. The purpose of the annotation has been to create training corpora for machine learning systems for automatic extraction of English and Lithuanian cybersecurity terms. The paper presents the composition of the corpora compiled for terminology annotation, the functionalities of the annotation tool developed for the purpose of the project, the annotation guidelines and methodology, as well as the problems which have occurred during the annotation process (distinction between different categories of terms, terms and proper names, etc.) and the quantitative results of the annotation.

1. Introduction

Automatic terminology extraction (ATE) plays an important role in the specialised knowledge acquisition process and enables various knowledge management applications such as compilation of terminology and knowledge bases, development of ontologies, categorization and search of data and documents, generation of linked data, etc. (c.f.

Hätty & Schulte im Walde, 2018). In ATE projects, corpora with manually annotated terminology are extensively used for the development of ATE methods, most of which are currently based on deep learning systems (cf. Bada *et al.*, 2010; Qasemi Zadeh & Handschuh, 2014; Schumann & Fischer, 2016; Hätty *et al.*, 2017). Such corpora serve as training datasets for machine learning systems applied for terminology extraction. In addition, they provide a lot of valuable terminological data for research of conceptual, linguistic and pragmatic dimensions of terminology.

The paper presents the work on compilation of corpora with manually annotated cybersecurity terminology carried out by researchers of two universities in Lithuania: Vytautas Magnus University and Mykolas Romeris University within the framework of DVITAS project¹. The aim of the project has been to develop a methodology for automatic extraction of English and Lithuanian terms from parallel and comparable corpora, as well as to create a publicly available bilingual termbase. The cybersecurity (CS) domain has been chosen as a specialised domain for the project (see the description of the methodology of the whole project in Rackevičienė *et al.* 2021). The manually annotated training corpora have been used for development of ATE methods based on deep learning systems. The paper presents the composition of the corpora compiled for terminology annotation, the functionalities of the annotation tool developed for the purposes of the project, the annotation guidelines, as well as the problems which have occurred during the annotation process (distinction between different categories of terms, terms and proper names, etc.) and the quantitative results of the annotation.

2. Training corpora

The training corpora have been compiled on the basis of larger unannotated specialised cybersecurity corpora composed for terminology extraction: a parallel cybersecurity corpus composed of original texts in English and their translations into Lithuanian (1.4m

1 <https://klc.vdu.lt/dvitas/en>

words), and a comparable cybersecurity corpus composed of original texts in English and Lithuanian (4m words) (see the presentation of the corpora system in Utka *et al.* 2022).

The training corpora have been composed according to the same principles as the unannotated corpora. A parallel training corpus (102,583 words) and a comparable training corpus (231,061 words) have been compiled, the same text categories as in the unannotated corpora have been included, and their proportions have been determined by the proportions of the text categories in the unannotated corpora. While English and Lithuanian parts are almost equal in size (56,902 words and 45,681 words accordingly) in the parallel corpus, English and Lithuanian parts considerably differ in the comparable corpus (the size of the English part is 72,429 words, while the size of the Lithuanian part is 158,632 words). This is due to a big need for Lithuanian cybersecurity annotated data as no datasets with such annotations exist. In contrast, datasets with English cybersecurity term annotations do exist and can be used for analysis and for training (e. g. Bridges *et al.* 2013, Cariola 2015, Hanks *et al.* 2022).

The compilation of two types of corpora (comparable and parallel) allowed to have a much bigger variety of text types and discourses. The parallel English-Lithuanian data in the cybersecurity domain are restricted to official documents, most of which are the EU legislative acts and related documents: their English versions and Lithuanian translations. The EU document collection encompasses **binding legislative documents** (regulations and directives adopted by the European Parliament and Council), and **non-binding legislative documents** (communications and recommendations by the European Commission).

The comparable data are much more diverse: original English and original Lithuanian texts on cybersecurity are produced in various discourses: **legislative** (legislative acts and related documents), **administrative & informative** (reports, information bulletins and recommendations issued by cybersecurity agencies and other CS practitioners), **academic** (textbooks and research papers), and **media**

(mass and specialised media articles) (c.f. discourses on cybercrime in Wall, 2007). Table 1 provides the time period covered by the training corpora, their sizes, composition and proportions of the included text categories.

EN-LT Comparable Training Corpus Size: 231,061 words		EN-LT Parallel Training Corpus Size: 102,583 words	
Time period: 2011-2021			
Legislative texts (legislative acts and related documents)	20 %	The EU legislative texts which are binding documents (regulations and directives adopted by the European Parliament and Council)	60 %
Administrative & informative texts (reports, recommendations, etc. by CS practitioners)	20 %		
Academic texts (textbooks and research papers)	20 %	The EU legislative texts which are non-binding documents (communications and recommendations of the European Commission)	40 %
Media texts (mass and specialized media articles)	40 %		

TABLE 1 – *Composition of training corpora*

The balancing of the text categories in English and Lithuanian parts of the comparable corpus has been one of the biggest challenges in the corpora compilation process as availability of English and Lithuanian original texts of the selected types and discourses differs. The most available texts in both languages have been those created in the media discourse; therefore, they constitute the biggest proportion of the corpus.

3. Annotators, annotation tool and guidelines

The annotation of the training corpora has been performed by 4 annotators, all of them are terminology researchers. During the whole

annotation process, the annotators have been assisted by a cybersecurity expert who has been validating the annotation and consulting the annotators.

For the purposes of the annotation work, the special user-friendly *QuickTag* tool has been developed. It has been several times updated after the pilot annotations performed by the annotation team to serve best the purposes of the project. The current version of the software provides a toolkit for annotation of terms and proper names used in monolingual texts and bilingual parallel texts. Functionalities of the tool help annotators adding various types of metadata about lexical units used in coherent texts.

FIG. 1 – *Annotation in QuickTag*

```
(3)<START:kse|undefined|undefined>Cybersecurity
incidents<END> can trigger a broader crisis, impacting sectors
of activity beyond <START:ksse|undefined|undefined>network
and information systems<END> and
<START:ksse|undefined|undefined>communication
networks<END>; any appropriate response must rely upon both
<START:kse|undefined|underfined>cyber and non-cyber mitigation
activities<END>.</seg></tuv>
```

```
(3) <START:ks|undefined|undefined>kibernetinio
saugumo incidentai<END> gali sukelti platesnę
krizę ir paveikti sektorius, kurių veikla neapsiriboja
<START:kss|undefined|undefined>tinklais ir informacinėmis
sistemomis<END> ar <START:kss|undefined|undefined>ryšių
tinklais<END>; bet koks tinkamas reagavimas turi būti
grindžiamas ir <START:ks|undefined|undefined>kibernetinėmis,
ir nekibernetinėmis poveikio mažinimo priemonėmis<END>;</
seg></tuv> </tu>
```

FIG. 2 – *Annotation tags in a TMX file*

The main functionality of *QuickTag* allows tagging terms and proper names with pre-configured tags, as well as adding additional attributes of various features for the tagged lexical units. In addition, the tool enables to decompose complex terms and proper names and annotate separately nested lexical units. Figure 1 shows the annotation window in *QuickTag*, while Figure 2 demonstrates how the applied tags were used in a parallel file that is created in the Translation Memory Exchange (TMX) format.

Detailed annotation guidelines have been developed in order to achieve maximum consistency in the annotation process. The guidelines determined the scope of the annotation, which consists of 3 categories of lexical units that reflect the conceptual and pragmatic aspects of cybersecurity lexis:

1. **Intra-subject terminology**, i.e. terminology specific to the cybersecurity domain;
2. **Inter-subject terminology**, i.e. terminology used both in the cybersecurity domain and other closely related domains, e.g. certain ICT terms;
3. **Proper names** denoting named entities relevant to the CS domain (c.f. Hätyy *et al.*, 2017; Hätyy & Schulte im Walde, 2018).

The special tags have been created for each of the categories (see Table 2):

Annotation categories	Tags
Lithuanian terms of the CS domain English terms of the CS domain	KS KSE
Lithuanian terms of the domains related to CS English terms of the domains related to CS	KSS KSSE
Proper names (both Lithuanian and English) relevant to the CS domain	KSDP

TABLE 2 – *The annotation categories and their tags*

Linguistic restrictions have been imposed in the guidelines: it has been determined to annotate only those terms which are nouns, noun phrases, abbreviations (acronyms or initialisms), which function as nouns, and combinations of abbreviations and nouns/noun phrases. Thus, specialised verbs and verb phrases have been excluded from the annotation.

In addition, some other features of terms and proper names have been annotated using additional attributes for linguistic research purposes, see Table 3. These attributes allow analysing some peculiarities of term usage: usage of incomplete term forms, abbreviations, EN borrowings in LT texts, as well as analysing semantic classes of proper names. The attributes have not been used for training of neural networks.

Features of terms and proper names annotated using additional attributes	Examples with additional attributes
Incomplete forms of terms	<i>ataka</i> [attribute: incomplete term, comment: full term ‘kibernetinė ataka’]
Abbreviations (acronyms and initialisms)	<i>CERT</i> [attribute: acronym/initialism]

Features of terms and proper names annotated using additional attributes	Examples with additional attributes
English unlocalised terms/parts of terms in Lithuanian texts	„phishing“ [attribute: unlocalised EN borrowing] „Man-in-the-middle“ ataka [attribute: EN-LT hybrid]
Semantic classes of proper names	NKSC [attribute: institution name] <i>Lietuvos Respublikos kibernetinio saugumo įstatymas</i> [attribute: document name]

TAB. 3 – *Additional features of terms and proper names and their attributes in the annotated dataset*

Complex terms and proper names have been decomposed and lexical units nested in them have been annotated separately:

- terms in complex proper names, e.g.:
National cybersecurity centre → *cybersecurity*,
- terms in complex terminological combinations, e.g.:
ICT products, services and processes → *ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes*,
device and configuration management → *device management and configuration management*.

QuickTag also allows exporting tagged lexical units to *MS Excel* spreadsheet file, in which it provides structured lists of tagged units with statistical data and context extracts. The *MS Excel* files have enabled to study the annotation results, detect occurring problems and discuss them, as well as to perform terminological analysis of the annotated data. The final version of the annotated datasets has been converted into BIO tagging format, which has been used for training neural networks.

4. Problems of annotation

Despite the handy software and detailed guidelines, the annotation process has constantly posed various problems concerning delimitation of the domain, boundaries of a term, term – proper name distinction, etc. Some of the major problems are discussed in the subsections below.

4.1. Delimiting the domain: intra-subject term or inter-subject term?

One of the biggest challenges during the annotation has been distinction between intra-subject terminology (terminology of the CS domain) and inter-subject terminology (terminology used in both CS and other domains) as it has required thorough analysis of the definitions and usage of the terms, as well as constant cooperation with the cybersecurity expert.

The guidelines for distinction of the cybersecurity terminology have been developed based on the existing cybersecurity knowledge graphs and expert consultations. Major thematic groups have been distinguished in each category of terms:

Intra-subject terminology: designations of concepts referring to malicious cyber activities, measures and people involved in such activities (e.g., *cyber attack*, *DDoS attack*, *APT attack*, *GPS spoofing*, *GPS jamming*, *APT group*); cybersecurity activities, measures and people involved in such activities (e.g., *cybersecurity certification*, *threat assessment*, *incident response*, *information security officer*); software vulnerabilities which might cause cybersecurity risks (e.g., *security vulnerability*, *security misconfiguration*, *cryptographic failure*).

Inter-subject terminology: designations of concepts referring to network and information systems and data stored in them, as well as digital products and services using network and information systems (e.g., *NIS (network and information system)*, *ICT device (information and communication technology device)*, *power grid*); various network functionalities which might have vulnerabilities (e.g., *RDP (Remote*

Desktop Protocol), *SMB (Server Message Block)*, *DNS (Domain Name System)*).

The terms of the first group (intra-subject terminology) designate fundamental concepts of the cybersecurity domain. Meanwhile, the terms of the second group (inter-subject terminology) denote concepts which function both in the cybersecurity domain and other domains (mainly, ICT domain). They refer to targets of malicious cyber activities which encompass any network and information system, as well as any network functionality which may allow accessing the system and taking it under control.

The distinction between intra- and inter-subject terminology has been introduced to analyse what domains are mostly related to and dependent on cybersecurity. As one could expect, ICT terms have been often present in the texts and have had to be ascribed to either intra-subject or inter-subject terminology groups, e.g.:

Fraudsters can manipulate the Internet traffic, including regular Internet browsing, emails, SSH, remote desktop, RDP video and voice calls, and software updates.

This sentence contains terms which are specific to the ICT domain; however, in the given context, they are related to security issues: *Internet traffic*, *Internet browsing*, *emails*, *SSH*, *remote desktop*, *RDP video*, *voice calls*, *software updates* denote concepts referring to network activities and functionalities which may be used by a hacker to defraud and manipulate the victim. Thus, in this particular context, concepts, which belong to a much broader ICT domain and represent common activities and functionalities, acquire additional characteristics: they refer to entities which might be maliciously used as means for offensive cyber operations by cyber perpetrators. In such cases, a boundary between intra- and inter-terminology becomes blurred, as the concepts representing common ICT domain entities become integral elements of cybersecurity events.

In this and similar situations, it has been difficult to achieve inter-annotator agreement because attribution of such borderline terms to a certain domain has been very context dependent. However, it has

been necessary to achieve the agreement among annotators to develop consistently annotated corpora which are necessary for smooth training of neural network models. Having considered the whole picture of the annotation, the decision has been taken to ascribe such terms, as described above, to inter-subject terminology as they designate concepts that represent common ICT activities and functionalities and acquire specific additional characteristics only when used in the cybersecurity context.

Thus, the distinction between intra- and inter-subject terminology has required thorough analysis of the definitions of the terms and context of their usage, as well as expert knowledge. Besides, in order to achieve inter-annotator agreement, regular discussions and unification procedures have been necessary.

4.2. Distinguishing between general and individual concepts: a term or a proper name?

Another annotation problem has been related to ascribing lexical units to the categories of terms and proper names. This categorization has been based on distinction between general and individual concepts.

In ISO standards on terminology work and science, a general concept is defined as a concept which corresponds to a set of potentially unlimited number of objects which form a group by reason of shared properties, while an individual concept is described as a concept that corresponds to a unique object or a composition of entities considered to form a unique object (ISO 1087: 2019; ISO 704: 2022). In the standards, four types of concept designations are distinguished: terms, appellations, proper names and symbols. The provided definitions indicate that terms and appellations (which are considered to be a type of terms) designate general concepts, while proper names – individual concepts; symbols can designate both types of concepts. The distinction between terms and appellations is based on properties of objects they represent. As it is indicated in ISO 1087, 2019, appellations represent a group of objects whose relevant properties are identical, e.g. *Nokia 7 Plus* (mobile phone), *Adobe Acrobat X Pro* (software), *Road King*

(motorcycle). Thus, one may conclude that terms and appellations designate general concepts, but the former represent groups of objects with similar properties, while the latter represent groups of objects with identical properties.

In our annotation work, the distinction has been made only between terms and proper names; appellations have been annotated as terms. However, the distinction between the categories has not always been straightforward.

One of the complicated cases has been the annotation of the abbreviations denoting cybersecurity response teams: *CSIRT* (*Computer Security Incident Response Team*), *CERT* (*Computer Emergency Response Team*), *CRRT* (*Cyber Rapid Response Team*). They are also used with various attributes indicating their types or countries in which they operate, e.g. *DefCERT* (CERT responsible for defence of military IT infrastructure), *national CERT*, *civil CERT*, *national CSIRT*, *CERT-EU*, *CERT-LT*.

These teams are established by different institutions and documents: *CSIRT Network* was established by NIS Directive 2016 (CSIRTs Network, n.d.). *CERT* is a registered trademark belonging to Carnegie Mellon University (Carnegie Mellon University Software Engineering Institute, 2021(b)). *CRRTs* were established by the Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO) framework members (Skardinskas, 2020).

The analysis of the relevant websites revealed that cybersecurity experts encourage to use *CSIRT* as a generic term, while *CERT* may be used only by organizations that are licensed to use this trademark: “*CERT has been a registered mark owned by Carnegie Mellon University since 1997. Organizations that we have licensed to use the CERT mark may use it in both their short and long names. <...> Do not use CERT as a generic term to refer to a category of organizations. Use the term ‘computer security incident response teams (CSIRTs)’ when referring to organizations that perform these kinds of activities*” (Carnegie Mellon University Software Engineering Institute, 2021(a)). These realities show the attempts by the domain experts to systematise concepts and ascribe functions to them: *CSIRT* is being positioned as

a term designating a generic concept in relation to specific concepts referring to specific cyber response teams.

The abbreviation *CRRT* also refers to specific response teams. They are international teams which are on standby on a rotational basis and are ready to respond to a cyber-attack immediately in case it occurred in one of the partners' countries (Skardinskas, 2020). *CRRT* is also used as an abbreviation of the name of the project which has established these response teams: "Cyber Rapid Response Teams and Mutual Assistance in Cyber Security". This project is developed within the framework of Permanent Structured Cooperation in Security and Defence Policy (PESCO), initiated and, after the approval of the Council of the EU, led by Lithuania (Šakūnas & Vasiliauskaitė, 2020). In texts, *CRRT* is often used in combination with the abbreviation *PESCO* referring to the above-mentioned framework: *PESCO CRRT*, *PESCO CRRT team*, *PESCO CRRT project*, *PESCO CRRT annual meeting*, *PESCO CRRT incident report*.

The described realities have made attribution of the abbreviations to the categories of terms or proper names complicated. The main criterium for their categorization has been the distinction between general and individual concepts defined in ISO terminology standards which is based on concept representation either of groups of objects with shared (similar or identical) properties or of unique objects. Having considered all the collected information on the response teams, it has been decided that all above-described response teams represent groups of objects whose basic properties are identical; thus, they are represented by general concepts which are designated by appellations. As appellations are regarded as a subtype of terms in ISO terminology standards, it has been decided to annotate them as terms.

The problem has remained with *CRRT* which is a homonym and may refer both to a certain type of a response team and the PESCO project. In some contexts, this distinction has not been clear and the meaning of the abbreviation could have been interpreted in both ways. Considering all factors, it has been decided to annotate *CRRT* as a term in all cases in order to achieve consistency in the annotated corpora.

4.3. Determining the language of a term: English or Lithuanian?

One more annotation problem has been related to linguistic categorization of terms according to their language. This problem occurred in the Lithuanian part of the training corpora. In Lithuanian texts, a considerable number of English terms are used. Most of them are used in bracketed insertions. However, some of them are used as integral parts of Lithuanian sentences:

- English terms used in original form in Lithuanian sentences:
Dofoil <...> yra naudojamas brukalo siuntimui, “phishing” puslapių ir kenkėjiško programinio kodo platinimui... ‘Dofoil <...> is used for sending spam, spread of “phishing” pages and malware...’
- English terms in semi-localised form in Lithuanian sentences:
*Manau, šiais laikais tai yra dominuojantis atakos būdas, su kuriuo susidurs dauguma žmonių – vienokio ar kitokio pavidalo **phishingas**.* ‘I think these days it’s the dominant mode of attack that most people will face – phishing in one form or another.’

Such English terms behave as Lithuanian words: they perform syntactic functions of constituents of Lithuanian syntactic structures and some of them even have Lithuanian endings.

The decision has been taken to distinguish between English terms in bracketed insertions and English terms used as integral parts of Lithuanian sentences. The former have been tagged as English terms, while the latter have been tagged as Lithuanian terms with additional attribute “unlocalised borrowing” or (if they constitute a part of an English-Lithuanian term) “English-Lithuanian hybrid”. These additional linguistic annotations have been made for linguistic research purposes and have not been used in neural network training.

5. Annotation results

The total amount of annotations for the main categories (intra-subject terminology, inter-subject terminology, and proper names) in the comparable corpus is 16,270. The number of English annotations

is 4,011, while the number of Lithuanian annotations is 12,259. As it was indicated in Section 2, the annotation of Lithuanian terms and proper names has been the primary goal of the project as no Lithuanian datasets with cybersecurity annotations have been developed before. The annotated comparable corpus contains: 2,495 EN and 7,578 LT annotations of terms of the CS domain, 1,259 EN and 3,311 LT annotations of terms of the related domains, 257 EN and 1,363 LT annotations of proper names. The collected data have allowed to perform comparative density calculations of terms in the English and Lithuanian datasets, the results of which are presented in Figure 3. The analysis shows that lexical units of all three categories have more dense distribution within the Lithuanian corpus than within the English corpus.

The total amount of annotations for the main categories (intra-subject terminology, inter-subject terminology and proper names) in the parallel corpus is 6,444: 3,219 English annotations and 3,225 Lithuanian annotations. The annotated parallel corpus contains: 1,670 EN and 1,667 LT annotations of terms of the CS domain, 665 EN and 691 LT annotations of terms of the related domains, 884 EN and 867 LT annotations of proper names. As in the case of comparable corpus, we have performed comparative density calculations of terms in the English and Lithuanian datasets, the results of which are presented in Figure 4. Obviously, the density of Lithuanian lexical units of all categories is higher than of English lexical units, due to differences in structural nature of languages, as analytic languages are more wordy than synthetic languages.

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FIG. 3 – *Density of CS intra-subject, inter-subject and proper name annotations in the English-Lithuanian comparable corpus*

FIG. 4 – *Density of CS intra-subject, inter-subject and proper name annotations in the English-Lithuanian parallel corpus*

The density of intra-subject and inter-subject terms is lower in the CS parallel corpus than in the comparable corpus for the both languages; however, the density of CS proper names is higher in the parallel corpus.

6. Final remarks

The development of the training corpora revealed that terminological annotation work requires extensive pilot studies in order to develop accurate and clear annotation schemes, intense teamwork in order to achieve consistent tagging, as well as quality assurance mechanisms for every annotation stage.

During the whole training corpus development process, close cooperation with an expert of the cybersecurity domain has been of vital importance. The expert support has been indispensable in the following stages: selection of the most relevant texts for compilation

of the corpora; delimiting the boundaries of the cybersecurity domain and determining the distinction between the cybersecurity terminology and terminology of the related domains, comprehension of concept characteristics necessary for their categorisation, and, finally, validation of the created annotations.

It should also be noted that inconsistencies in human annotation could be treated as valuable information that is important for capturing the problematic nature of terminology. The idea has been recently proposed by Plank (2022) and it is certainly worth serious consideration in human annotation tasks.

The developed corpora have been used as datasets for training deep learning systems developed for bilingual terminology extraction, the results of which will be provided in our future papers. In addition, the corpora provide multifaceted data and metadata which enable to perform quantitative and qualitative analyses of conceptual, linguistic and pragmatic dimensions of cybersecurity terminology in the English and Lithuanian languages (see the analysis of the Lithuanian dataset in Rackevičienė *et al.* 2022).

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Résumé

Cet article présente le travail de compilation de corpus parallèles et comparables anglais-lituanien dans lesquels le lexique de la sécurité informatique a été annoté manuellement. Le but de cette annotation est de préparer des collections de données pour l'apprentissage automatique à l'aide de réseaux de neurones en vue de l'extraction automatique des termes du domaine de la cybersécurité en anglais et en lituanien à partir de tels corpus. L'article présente la composition des corpus annotés, les fonctionnalités de l'outil développé pour effectuer le travail d'annotation, les principes et la méthodologie qui ont guidé l'annotation des termes, ainsi que les problèmes rencontrés durant ce processus (la distinction des différentes catégories de termes, entre termes et noms propres) et les résultats quantitatifs de l'annotation.